

The influence of storytelling communication on consumer buying decisions. A case of cinephiles at the Light Cinema, Bolton

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Abstract

Purpose: This study examines how storytelling communication influences the buying decisions of cinephiles at the Light Cinema, Bolton, UK, drawing on the Cultivation and Affective Disposition Theories.

Methods: A quantitative approach was employed, collecting data from 50 cinephiles at the Light Cinema, Bolton, UK, using purposive sampling. A 40-item Likert scale questionnaire was administered, and regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses and analyze the data.

Findings: Results indicate a positive but minimal relationship between storytelling communication and buying decisions. The marginal effect suggests that storytelling alone is not sufficient as a promotional tool and is most effective when combined with other marketing strategies.

Practical Implications: The study emphasizes the value of storytelling communication for marketing. While storytelling can enhance brand visibility and create emotional connections with consumers, it does not automatically translate into increased purchasing. Organizations, particularly during global economic challenges that threaten business survival, should strategically integrate storytelling with other elements of the marketing mix (4Ps) to maximize effectiveness.

Originality: While previous studies have highlighted the benefits of storytelling communication, few have investigated why some businesses continue to struggle despite engaging content. This study contributes by examining how storytelling impacts consumer buying decisions in a context of business survival amid widespread closures.

Keywords: Storytelling; Communication; Buying decisions; Cinephiles; Entrepreneurs; Business success

1. Introduction

The closure of TESCO stores due to lack of customer patronage, contrasted with Aldi's expansion plans, raises the question: "How do businesses succeed in a time when closures are increasingly common?" (GB News, 2023). In this context, amidst the ongoing cost-of-living crisis and widespread business failures, storytelling communication has gained prominence as a strategic tool for business success. Numerous studies highlight its role in preventing business closure, enhancing brand visibility, and fostering sustainable consumer loyalty (Lee et al., 2016; Hamelin et al., 2020; Sundin et al., 2018).

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As a hub for cinephiles, the Light Cinema attracts numerous movie enthusiasts with a deep engagement in film narratives, making them ideal participants for a study on consumer behavior. Additionally, the researcher's familiarity with the location, as a frequent movie-goer, facilitates a seamless environment for data collection.

1.1. Hypotheses

The following are the null hypotheses.

- H₀1: There is no relationship between storytelling communication as a marketing tool and consumer purchases at the Light Cinema, in Bolton.
- H₀2: There is no relationship between using storytelling communication as a marketing tool and influencing consumers buying decisions at the Light Cinema in Bolton.
- H₀3: There is no relationship between the use of storytelling communication as a sustained means of consumer awareness and engagement and cinephiles buying decision at the Light Cinema in Bolton.

2. Literature review

Storytelling communication plays a very important role in marketing by enabling entrepreneurs to establish meaningful connections between consumers and their brands, products, or services. Scholars such as Escalas (Jennifer) in *Advertising and Promotion: An Integrated Marketing Communications Perspective*, pioneering filmmaker Flaherty (Robert) in his landmark documentary *Nanook of the North*, and producer-director Kemp (David) in *The Best and the Brightest* have highlighted the significance of storytelling as an influential practice for shaping values and perceptions (Rosli et al., 2022). This underscores the importance of storytelling as a marketing tool for achieving business success. Whether conveying a message or influencing decision-making processes, effective storytelling can evoke emotions and empathy in audiences, surpassing traditional consumer appeals.

The effectiveness of brand storytelling lies in its ability to engage audiences by delivering messages that resonate deeply with target markets. Brands that align their campaign narratives with the experiences of their audience often enjoy enhanced sales and increased brand recognition. Notable examples include Nike's iconic "Just Do It" campaign in 1988, Apple's "Think Different" campaign in 1997, and McDonald's catchy "I'm Loving It" slogan introduced in 2003. By employing storytelling techniques that emphasize personalization, emotional appeal, diversity, inclusion, adventure, anticipation, and excitement, brands have successfully expanded their customer base and encouraged repeat business, fostering lasting loyalty.

In contemporary marketing communication strategies, storytelling has become increasingly vital. Unlike instructional narratives, captivating storytelling evokes emotional responses, which are crucial for effective communication. Through storytelling, a brand's unique values and principles are conveyed, fostering personal bonds with consumers.

Scholars such as Ahuja and Loura (2022) and Anaza, Kemp, Briggs, and Borders (2020) emphasize the importance of narrative stories in connecting with, persuading, and enhancing customer-brand interactions. Storytelling empowers brands to engage consumers in co-creating brand values, reinforcing connections, and instilling confidence in products. Consequently, narrative storytelling serves as a powerful tool for marketers seeking to strengthen relationships with consumers and influence their purchasing decisions.

In today's marketplace, storytelling communication continues to be a crucial marketing tool that shapes consumer behaviour and fosters meaningful connections with customers. Research demonstrates that storytelling can significantly affect buying decisions, which explains why numerous studies have explored its influence through media platforms and word-of-mouth (WoM) communication. For instance, Hauff et al. (2014) highlight the advantages of using storytelling to build a customer base, while Heine and Berghaus (2014) illustrate how storytelling content on social media and WoM amplifies customer experiences by sharing them with a wider audience. Rosli et al. (2022) further underlines the significance of WoM interactions, including product reviews and recommendations, as tools that drive referrals and influence purchasing behaviour. Storytelling, therefore, plays a critical role in shaping consumer buying behaviour and provides consumers with valuable information about brands and products (Sundin et al., 2018).

Informational elements in advertisements also influence consumer attitudes (Sundin et al., 2018). Conveying information that appeals to consumers enhances brand visibility, engages customers, and promotes loyalty (Rosli et al., 2022; Chautard & Collin-Lachaud, 2019). Storytelling is particularly effective in this regard, as it engages audiences and strengthens product recall. Singh and Uthayakumar-Cumarasamy (2022) emphasize that the entertainment factor

inherent in storytelling is a key driver of improved product recall, while Kessous et al. (2015) similarly highlight its influence on customer behaviour.

Consequently, storytelling communication has become an essential marketing tool for promoting brand impact on consumer purchasing intentions (Hamelin et al., 2020). Its entertaining aspects enhance brand attitudes, leading to increased visibility and long-term customer satisfaction (Lee et al., 2016). Understanding the impact of storytelling on advertising, consumer behaviour, and brand engagement is therefore crucial for evaluating its effectiveness in driving purchase intentions.

In summary, storytelling communication significantly influences consumer buying behaviour, brand engagement, and decision-making. It promotes product loyalty, conveys valuable information, and enhances consumer engagement and attitudes towards brands. This research aims to further explore the multifaceted dimensions of storytelling communication to understand its relationship with consumer behaviour and purchasing decisions.

3. Methods and Methodology

Figure 1 Research design

The study employs two statistical analytical methods. The descriptive method, illustrated in Figures 3.1 to 3.4, outlines the sequential research approach adopted and the various components of the major classes within the research questionnaire. Questions 1 to 11 of the instrument capture demographic information. In addition, regression analysis, as part of inferential statistics, was utilized to examine the influence of storytelling communication on cinephiles' buying decisions.

Primary data were collected through a structured survey. A quantitative approach was adopted, targeting 50 cinephiles at the Light Cinema, Bolton, UK, using purposive sampling and a 40-item Likert scale questionnaire (Crespo et al., 2023). The sample of 50 participants represented 10% of the total population of 500, which is considered sufficient for analysis (Lee et al., 2016). A 100% response rate was achieved.

The questionnaire was designed to cover all relevant measures related to the study variables, as illustrated in Figures 3.2, 3.3, and 3.4. Responses were recorded using a five-point Likert scale, ranging from *strongly agree* (5) to *strongly disagree* (1). To minimize interpretation bias, the research questions were framed in simple English, with explanations

provided for technical terms. Response bias was further reduced by using the structured Likert scale format (Westland, 2022).

Prior to the main study, the instrument was piloted with five cinephiles to ensure clarity and comprehension. The study employed a cross-sectional time horizon and utilized a self-developed 40-item instrument tailored to an all-inclusive age range, a specific geographical location, restricted boundaries, frequency of engagement, and a case study approach.

4. Statistical Analysis and Findings

4.1. Inferential Statistics: Regression Analysis

4.1.1. Hypothesis testing

Decision Criteria

The co-efficient of β value represents the significance of relationship that subsists between the study variables. Where a positive value is obtained, the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Where the β value exceeds 0.5, it is evidence of a high degree of positive relationship, while a β value less than 0.5 indicates a weak degree of positive relationship. Alternatively, the null hypothesis will be accepted where the β value is negative, indicating no relationship among variables.

- **Hypothesis one**

There is no significant relationship between storytelling communication as an effective marketing informative tool and cinephiles' buying at the Light Cinema, Bolton.

$$f(SC) = \alpha + \beta_1 SC + \epsilon$$

Table 1 Model Summary of Regression and Coefficients Analysis for Storytelling as an Informative Communication Tool

Model Summaryb						
	R	R2	Adjusted R2	Std. Error	Durbin-Watson	
	0.096a	0.009	-0.011	4.110	1.918	
Predictors: (Constant), SC						
Dependent Variable: Informative Communication Tool						
Coefficients						
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
	(Constant)	14.442	2.537		5.692	0.000
	SC	0.338	0.504	0.096	0.671	0.505
a. Dependent Variable: Informative Communication Tool						

Source: Researcher's fieldwork (2023)

Figure 2 Informative Communication Scatter diagram

Hypothesis one was evaluated using research question one to give:

R = 0.096 establishes that storytelling as an informative communication tool has a negligible to very weak positive, linear relationship. Brands that tend to use storytelling to inform their customers about new or existing developments to improve their buying decision will enjoy a negligible increase at $R^2 = 0.9\%$. Furthermore, a negative value of adjusted $R^2 = -0.011$, suggests that facts and other alternative means of information may even be preferred as an informative means of connecting with customers in contrast to stories when new information needs to be communicated. The negative sign connotes that for every iota of brand information communicated through stories, the intended audience absorbs less information.

A β value of 0.338 evidence a weak, positive relationship between storytelling as an effective marketing informative tool and cinephiles' buying at the Light Cinema, Bolton. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. The positive but negligible to weak statistical relationship implies that storytelling is not a standalone component for the actualization of effective marketing information communication. This position is prominent in the findings of Huang et al. (2023) who reiterated that unless entrepreneurs are knowledgeable in how to deploy high predictive powers in applying the right narratives in their ads and marketing strategies, companies' storytelling may be void of communicating any message. They argue that information can only be effective when the sender communicates, and the receiver understands.

- **Hypothesis two:**

There is no significant relationship between storytelling as a marketing promotion tool and cinephiles' buying decision at the Light Cinema, Bolton.

$$f(SC) = \alpha + \beta_2 SC + \varepsilon$$

Model Summary^b

Table 2 Model Summary of Regression and Coefficients Analysis for Storytelling as a Marketing Promotion Tool

	R	R2	Adjusted R2	Std. Error	Durbin-Watson
	0.175a	0.031	0.010	61.992	1.203
a. Predictors: (Constant), Storytelling Communication					
b. Dependent Variable: Marketing Promotion Tool					
Coefficients					

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	135.705	38.267		3.546	0.001
SC	9.346	7.602	0.175	1.229	0.225
a. Dependent Variable: Marketing Promotion Tool					

Hypothesis two was evaluated using research questions two to generate:

R = 0.175 establishes that storytelling as a marketing promotion tool has a weak, positive linear relationship. The positive relationship reveals that as stories abound as a means of marketing promotion tool, cinephiles will be influenced to make a buying decision. However, the influence would be very marginal at R² = 3.1%, owing to the weak, positive relationship that subsists. The R² shows that storytelling can only explain 3.1% of a brand’s marketing promotion. Hence, 96.9% awareness generated by marketing promotion are due to other external factors beyond storytelling. This is further evidenced by the adjusted R² which reveals that only 1% of the buying decision is achieved with storytelling. Findings therefore evidence that other parameters beyond storytelling influence the buying decision of cinephiles as corroborated by the value of adjusted R² = 0.010. This means storytelling can only account for a 1% variance among variables.

From the findings above, a β value of 9.346 shows a positive and very strong relationship among study variables. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternate hypothesis which states that there is a significant relationship between storytelling communication as a marketing promotion tool and cinephiles’ buying decision at the Light Cinema, Bolton is accepted. This pointer is emphasized by Richard Branson, a top global entrepreneur when he highlighted that the success of any entrepreneur depends on their ability to tell stories. The better the brand storytelling communication is at engaging the consumers, the more successful the organization will be, because storytelling communication is the apex of marketing promotion (Taylor, 2021; McCall et al., 2019).

• **Hypothesis three:**

There is no significant relationship between the use of storytelling communication as a sustained means of consumer awareness and engagement and cinephiles’ buying decision at the Light Cinema, Bolton.

Sustained means of consumer awareness and engagement.

$$f(SC) = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{ Storytelling Communication} + \epsilon$$

Table 3 Model Summary of Regression Analysis for Storytelling as a Sustained Means of Consumer Awareness and Engagement

Model Summaryb					
Model	R	R2	Adjusted R2	Std. Error	Durbin-Watson
1	0.137a	0.019	-0.002	4.104	2.108
. Predictors: (Constant), SC					
b. Dependent Variable: Consumer Awareness and Engagement					

Table 4 Regression Coefficients for Storytelling as a Sustained Means of Consumer Awareness and Engagement

Coefficients					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		

(Constant)	13.255	2.533		5.233	0.000
SC	0.483	0.503	0.137	0.959	0.342
a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Awareness and Engagement					

Source: SPSS (2023)

Figure 3 Storytelling as a means of Consumer Awareness and Engagement Scatter diagram

Hypothesis three was evaluated using research question 3.

$R = 0.137$ establishes that storytelling as a sustained means of consumer awareness and engagement has a negligible to weak, positive linear relationship. The positive relationship reveals that as stories abound as a means of sustained awareness and engagement, brands may enjoy consumer retention and increased engagement. However, the influence is negligible at $R^2 = 1.9\%$, owing to the very weak relationship that subsists. R^2 shows that storytelling can only explain 1.9% of how brands sustain customers' awareness and engagement. Alternatively, 98.1% of customers retained by a brand is due to other external factors beyond storytelling. This is further evidenced by the adjusted R^2 which reveals storytelling as a sustained means of consumer engagement and awareness varies inversely at -0.2% .

A β value of 0.483 evidence a weak, positive relationship between storytelling communication and sustained means of consumer engagement and awareness. the null hypothesis is rejected.

The alternate hypothesis stating that there is a relationship between storytelling as a sustained means of consumer awareness and engagement in cinephiles' buying decision at the Light Cinema, Bolton is accepted. The relationship that subsists is a positive, weak linear relationship, not statistically sufficient to deploy storytelling as a stand-alone marketing promotion tool.

Table 5 Relationship of Research Objectives with Theory and Findings

Research Objective	Theoretical underpinnings	Findings
1). To identify the informative storytelling communication strategy deployed at the Light Cinema, Bolton to influence cinephiles' purchase decision.	Cultivation Theory	Null Hypothesis 1: Rejected. Cultivation theory proposes the inclusion of facts to stories over a long duration as an effective means of passing information to customers to improve buying decisions. This is why IBM stands out.

2). To determine how storytelling communication as a marketing promotion tool can influence cinephiles' purchase decision at the Light Cinema, Bolton that will enhance consumer patronage.	Affective Disposition Theory (ADT)	Null Hypothesis 2: Rejected ADT theory postulates that brands work in conjunction with consumers using stories together with other marketing tools to create an emotional appeal such as seen in Google and Apple brand success stories.
3). To establish if storytelling communication can serve as a sustained means of achieving consumer awareness and engagement among cinephiles at the Light Cinema, Bolton.	Affective Disposition Theory	Null Hypothesis 3: Rejected. Findings align with the ADT, which evidence that once storytelling breaks the jinx, by arousing emotional stimulation in consumers, brands can enhance buying decisions by deploying additional variables. BMW and Rolex are examples.

Source: Study findings (2023)

Table 5. summarizes the study findings by linking the research objective with the underpinning theories and findings to establish a strategic map which emphasize that storytelling is not the sole marketing component that aids in the achievement of a sustainable buying decision. The research finding aligns with the work by Taylor (2021), who noted that the ability of organizations to retain their customers in and out of season is a complex aggregation of different marketing components and strategies. Gómez-Suárez et al. (2017) highlighted that loyal customers who continually engage in buying from brands constitute the life wire every organization desires.

4.2. Interpretation, Synthesis and Discussion of findings

Table 6 Summary of Empirical Studies on Storytelling and Consumer Buying Behaviour

Publication title	Author	Findings evidence increased patronage through:
<i>Long-duration Storytelling: Study of Factors Influencing Retention Ability of Brands</i>	Dhote, T., & Kumar, V. (2019).	The inculcation of storytelling into the 4Ps of marketing (product, price, place, promotion) enhances brand patronage.
Storytelling in Marketing: A Brand Perspective	Arens, Z. G. (2024)	Effective use of storytelling in collaboration with the 4Ps increases the value proposition of a product or service.
Tell me a story: The role of narrative transportation and the C-suite in B2B advertising	Anaza, N. A., Kemp, E., Briggs, E., & Borders, A. L. (2020)	Deploying storytelling communication and 4Ps on consumer behavior and brand perception culminates in successful marketing campaigns.
Storytelling is not just for marketing: Cultivating a storytelling culture throughout the organization	Kemp, A., Gravois, R., Syrdal, H., & McDougal, E. (2023)	The use of case studies to explain how the integration of case studies into the traditional marketing mix boosts brand engagement.
Rethinking communication: integrating storytelling for increased stakeholder engagement in environmental evidence synthesis	Sundin, A., Andersson, K., & Watt, R. (2018).	The psychological principles behind storytelling can be leveraged in consonance with the 4Ps of marketing to create successful marketing campaigns that resonate with consumers.

Source: Compilation of empirical findings' (2023)

Empirical review of contemporary literature as summarized in Table 4.2 have revealed that storytelling communication is not a standalone marketing component that influences buying decision. Table 4.2 is further strengthened by the works of McCall et al. (2019) and Dhote & Kumar (2019) that argue that while stories contribute to organizational success, companies should not solely emphasize storytelling to the detriment of other marketing components, but endeavour to

deploy sufficient resources into areas of marketing such as enhancing product quality, flexibility of prices and accessible location storytelling as to achieve desired buying decision. Moin (2020) explained that companies' inability to separate the contributions of storytelling to organizational success from other promotional parameters has led to huge and misplaced investments into advertisements which end up not generating the anticipated requisite returns. Hence, the spike witnessed in business collapse. He noted that the continuous emphasis solely on the use of storytelling to the detriment of other related marketing promotional tools has been the underlying cause of why companies fail to benefit from the benefits of storytelling. Heine & Berghaus (2014) also stated that the inadequate knowledge of how to effectively apportion the right resources in the right proportion to the various marketing promotional tools in conjunction with storytelling contributes to organizations' inability to generate leads through the deployment of stories. This may therefore not be unconnected with why (Brooks et al., 2021) while advocating for policies to be put in place to standardize the effective use of storytelling, also encouraged entrepreneurs to equip themselves with the knowledge of its usage so as not to emphasize one marketing component to the detriment of others. When the right mix of each component is achieved, organizations would become industry giants in their field like Coca-Cola, Google, and Airbnb, among others.

The foregoing was not supported by Hauff et al. (2014) who maintain that storytelling may sometimes be necessary to stand alone as a marketing promotion for organizational effectiveness. But in contradicting Hauff's view, scholars such as Chautard & Collin-Lachaud (2019) emphasized that for storytelling to aid in the increase of revenue, other marketing promotional factors such as packaging, place and quality of product being advertised play a critical role. They argue that no amount of effective storytelling can suffice to transform a fake product into a luxury product and vice versa. Hence, rather than position storytelling as a standalone marketing tool, it should be supported with other relevant promotional tools to achieve organizational success, critics maintain.

The study has established from discussions and data analyzed on one common underlying fact which is that storytelling, whether positioned in conjunction with other marketing promotion tools or as a stand-alone marketing tool contributes towards effective marketing promotion for organizational success.

5. Conclusion

The surge by entrepreneurs in the use of storytelling seems not to result in envisaged organizational success as the number of business collapses continues to skyrocket. Hence, entrepreneurs have become averse to business investments. Information available on Gov.UK (2023) evidence that over 76% of businesses collapse within the first 3 years of incorporation. As brands continue to flood the digital space with varying storytelling amidst colossal business collapse, the research analyzed how storytelling communication influences buying decisions. The objective was to understand how to use effective storytelling to mitigate business failures and encourage more entrepreneurial investments with the aim of improving the overall global economy.

The study concludes that:

- i. Storytelling is a veritable marketing promotion tool engineering business success, though not necessarily as a standalone component.
- ii. By understanding the art and science in the deployment of storytelling, entrepreneurs can enjoy sustainable consumer awareness and engagement and an endearing means of increased revenue. Hence, the onus is on entrepreneurs to engage in regular training to be abreast of consumer preferences to align the appropriate stories that resonate with the target audience.
- iii. In addition, the study revealed that even though stories are effective, marketers should desist from using storytelling as an informative tool. With a negligible relationship subsistent between storytelling and informative components, it is evident that facts are still preferable as informative tools. Hence, organizations should ensure a proper blend of storytelling intertwined with facts to achieve organizational aims and objectives.

This study has contributed immensely to the body of knowledge by unearthing that even though storytelling contributes to impacting consumer preferences towards achieving organizational success, it is not a stand-alone marketing component. Hence, the application and success of storytelling lie in its understanding and effective utilization in conjunction with other marketing tools in the right proportion as confirmed by Chautard & Collin-Lachaud (2019), otherwise, the outcome will be a meaningless cluster of "noisy ads" that would deflate consumers' morale from patronage.

In addition, the study has unveiled that man as an emotional being, tends to tilt towards irrational buying decisions when exposed to inspirational or nostalgic ads, which culminate in impulsive purchases with no rational justification for their buying preferences. Hence, entrepreneurs have leveraged the “emotional man” by identifying the right target audience, provoking the appropriate emotions in conjunction with effective campaign strategies and resonating narratives, to engender impulsive buying decisions that are beneficial to their organizations. This has become the dominant aspect of storytelling that has gained more prominence over other promotional strategies in the marketing domain, thereby seemingly promoting stories as a stand-alone marketing tool. Hence, the study has evidenced that the totality of quality products and services, accessible location, flexible pricing strategy, unique packaging and knowledgeable entrepreneurs are all critical in union with the successful deployment of effective storytelling to influence positive buying decisions that translates into organizational growth.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author(s) declare that there are no known financial, professional, or personal conflicts of interest that could have influenced the research process, analysis, interpretation of findings, or the publication of this manuscript.

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Appendix:

Demographics

- Gender
 - Male
 - Female
 - Prefer not to say
 - Others (specify)
- Age
 - 20 – 30
 - 31 – 40
 - 41 – 50
 - Above 50
- Status
 - Single
 - Married
 - Divorced
 - Separated
 - Prefer not to say
 - Others (specify)
- Education level
 - No formal education
 - GCSE/High School
 - College
 - University
 - Postgraduate
- What is your average monthly income?
 - Not working
 - On government benefit
 - Less than £1000 monthly
 - £1,000 - £2,000 monthly
 - Above £2,000 monthly
- What percentage of your monthly income is spent at the cinema every month?
 - Less than 10%
 - 10% - 25%
 - 26% - 50%
 - Above 50%
- How often do you visit the cinema?
 - Daily
 - Weekly
 - Bi-weekly
 - Occasionally (no trend: can be twice this week and four-time next week)
 - Once a month

Storytelling communication

Kindly tick one out of the five-points as appropriate (Note: Cinephiles means “movie-lovers”)

- | | |
|---------------------|---|
| ○ Strongly Agree | 5 |
| ○ Agree | 4 |
| ○ Undecided | 3 |
| ○ Disagree | 2 |
| ○ Strongly Disagree | 1 |

- Storytelling communication improves brand visibility
- Storytelling communication increases organisational revenue through increased patronage
- Storytelling communication aids in the achievement of a sustained means of consumer awareness and engagement

Storytelling communication as an informative communication tool

Kindly tick one out of the five-points as appropriate (Note: Cinephiles means “movie-lovers”)

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="radio"/> Strongly Agree | 5 |
| <input type="radio"/> Agree | 4 |
| <input type="radio"/> Undecided | 3 |
| <input type="radio"/> Disagree | 2 |
| <input type="radio"/> Strongly Disagree | 1 |

- Storytelling communication improves brand visibility among cinephiles.
- Allowing cinephiles to be part of organisational storytelling communication encourages increased buying decision.
- Storytelling communication allows cinephiles to resonate with the brand.
- Prolonged exposure of cinephiles to storytelling communication hastens their buying decision.
- The use of digital platforms to promote storytelling communication increases awareness among a wider coverage of cinephiles.
- Storytelling communication equips cinephiles with additional information about a brand.
- Storytelling communication affords movie lovers the opportunity to interact more effectively with the brand of their choice.
- Storytelling communication enables cinephiles to make a more balanced decision
- Well-crafted storytelling communication has all the essential ingredients to increase consumers’ buying decision and improve organisational revenue.
- Organisational interactions with cinephiles through storytelling communication allows for a better personal experience with consumer brand.

Storytelling communication as a marketing promotion tool

Kindly tick one out of the five-points as appropriate (Note: Cinephile means “movie lovers”)

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="radio"/> Very High Extent | 5 |
| <input type="radio"/> High Extent | 4 |
| <input type="radio"/> Unlikely | 3 |
| <input type="radio"/> Low Extent | 2 |
| <input type="radio"/> Very Low Extent | 1 |

- To what extent do you believe that the use of storytelling communication in the cinema have increased organisational revenue through increased patronage?

- To what extent do you believe storytelling communication is important in improving buying decision at cinemas in any jurisdiction?
- To what extent does the awareness of storytelling communication as a component of marketing strategy encourage cinephiles to buy more tickets?
- To what extent does storytelling communication as a marketing promotion tool contribute to cinephiles' understanding of emerging trends in marketing as to materialise in increased ticket purchase?
- To what extent do you believe the implementation of storytelling communication has encouraged improved ticket purchase at cinemas?
- To what extent do you believe that cinephiles are aware that the use of storytelling communication by organisations has been instrumental in their ticket purchase?
- To what extent do you believe that storytelling communication is the core marketing strategy that has improved cinephiles patronage?
- To what extent do you believe that that the addition and use of storytelling communication has been effective in marketing?
- To what extent do you think storytelling communication has improved consumers' understanding of a brand?
- To what extent do you believe that the source of consumers' attraction to a brand is the storytelling communication inherent in the brand?

Storytelling communication as a sustained means of consumer awareness and engagement

Kindly tick one out of the five-points as appropriate (Note: Cinephiles means "movie-lovers")

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="radio"/> Strongly Agree | 5 |
| <input type="radio"/> Agree | 4 |
| <input type="radio"/> Undecided | 3 |
| <input type="radio"/> Disagree | 2 |
| <input type="radio"/> Strongly Disagree | 1 |

- Storytelling communication provides a sustainable means of consumer awareness and engagement at cinemas.
- With the success associated with the knowledge of the application of storytelling communication, business collapse will reduce, and more entrepreneurs would be encouraged to engage in business.
- Entrepreneurs and the marketing department should promote the enhanced use of storytelling communication in achieving a sustained means of consumer awareness and engagement.
- By understanding the intricacies of how storytelling communication influences buying decision, consumers will be better positioned to make a balanced buying decision.
- By standardising organisational use of storytelling communication to influence buying decision, manipulation of consumers by entrepreneurs will be eliminated.
- The understanding of the critical component of storytelling communication that influences buying decision reduces the risk of business collapse due to low patronage.

- Regulating the contents of storytelling communication will enable entrepreneurs eschew manipulative tendencies, uphold integrity and transparency in their business dealings with consumers.
- By incorporating the interests of cinephiles in the planning of storytelling communication, organisations can achieve consumers enhanced and personalised experience with their brand.
- Organisations should increase the deployment of resources committed to encouraging storytelling communication to increase brand awareness and engagement.
- Educating entrepreneurs on the strategic use of storytelling communication will help achieve increased consumer awareness and patronage.